

Syntheses of Furo-Coumarins

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In view of the fact that many furo-coumarins such as kellin, psoralene, xanthotoxin etc., have received considerable attention on account of their therapeutic properties, it was considered worthwhile to prepare some new furo-coumarins and to evaluate their physiological activities.

o-Hydroxy acetyl coumarins were treated with bromoacetic ester and the resulting oxyacetates were hydrolysed to give the corresponding free acids. These acids were then cyclised to yield the desired furo-coumarins.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Methyl-5-hydroxy-6-acetyl coumarin was prepared from resacetophenone and ethyl-aceto-acetate¹. 4-Methyl-6-hydroxy-7-acetyl coumarin was similarly prepared from quinacetophenone and ethylacetoacetate. 4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyl coumarin was prepared from 4-methyl-7-acetoxy coumarin².

Preparation of furo-coumarins :

4,4'-Dimethyl furo(3',2'-5,6-)coumarin : Preparation of furo-coumarin from 5-hydroxy-6-acetyl coumarin involves preparation of the following intermediate compounds.

Ethyl-6-acetyl-5-coumarin oxyacetate : 4-Methyl-5-hydroxy-6-acetyl coumarin (8.8 g), bromoacetic ester (4.4 ml.) and potassium carbonate (5.2 g.) were refluxed in acetone for 4 hrs. The product obtained was recrystallised from ethanol.

The analytical data and m.p. of this compound and other related oxyacetates obtained in a similar manner are described in Table I.

TABLE I

Name of compounds	Yield %	M.P. °C	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Ethyl-6-acetyl-5-coumarin oxyacetate	55	153	62.92	63.15	5.12	5.26
Ethyl-7-acetyl-6-coumarin oxyacetate	45	80	62.98	63.15	5.15	5.26
Ethyl-8-acetyl-7-coumarin oxyacetate	60	111	63.07	63.15	5.02	5.26

6-Acetyl-5-coumarin oxyacetic acid : The above ester was refluxed with 5 per cent solution of sodium hydroxide for 3 hrs. On acidification the desired acid was obtained

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 131.

2. *Organic Syntheses*, Vol. 21, p. 22.

and was recrystallised from ethanol. The analytical data etc., of related compounds are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Name of compounds	Yield %	M.P. °C	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
6-Acetyl-5-coumarin oxyacetic acid	50	102	60.11	60.43	4.27	4.31
7-Acetyl-6-coumarin oxyacetic acid	45	134	60.21	60.43	4.12	4.31
8-Acetyl-7-coumarin oxyacetic acid	55	208	60.15	60.43	4.15	4.31

4,4'-Dimethyl furo (3',2'-5,6) coumarin : The above acid (3 g.) was heated with anhydrous sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (6 ml.) for 30 minutes. The product was washed with water recrystallised from ethanol. The analytical data, m.p. etc., of this compound and other furo-coumarins obtained similarly are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Name of compounds	Yield %	M.P. °C	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
4,4'-Dimethyl furo (3',2'-5,6) coumarin	45	158	72.23	72.56	4.95	5.10
4,4'-Dimethyl furo (3',2'-6,7) coumarin	35	103	72.31	72.56	4.85	5.10
4,4'-Dimethyl furo (3',2'-7,8) coumarin	40	154	72.29	72.56	4.91	5.10

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